

To Study the effect of PsychoNeurobics in curing Eye disorders and Improving Eye health

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Abstract

PsychoNeurobics is an emerging field of study wherein different aspects of physical and mental health is looked into. In this paper, we are looking to theorize the effect of it on eye health, mental health etc. in the subsequent paper, the author will present the experimental statistics around the said theory.

1. Introduction

Eyes are a ‘window to the soul.’ Experts mention that mental health can be intricately linked to eye health, and research also shows how eyes can be used to detect mental health issues. Whenever we are going through any sickness, stress or sadness, our family members and near

ones realize that and get the idea from our eyes only, without us uttering a single word regarding the situation. Thus, our mental condition affects our eyes and they become dull affecting our vision while experiencing such situations.

According to Dr. BK Chandrashekhar Sir our vision also gets affected with emotions and feelings. Thus, the reason behind vision change also depends on our mental health.

We do various kinds of physical exercises to keep the body fit, but it is also essential to maintain

our mental/ emotional health as well. Any type of mental stress or strain affects our mind and also vision ability. So, practicing eye exercises and practice of psycho Neurobics helps to relieve the stress and gives complete relaxation to our Eyes, Mind and Body.

2. Effects on Nervous System

The Central Nervous System is the integration and command centre of the human body. It contains - the brain, spinal cord, and the retinas of the eyes. The Cranial Nervous System nerves connect the brain to the eyes, ears, mouth, and other parts of the head.

Co-Relation between Brain and Eyes

The Cerebrum is one of the primary parts of the brain which has two hemispheres and each hemisphere controls all the activities done by opposite side of the hemisphere. These two hemispheres are divided into four lobes. They are: Frontal lobe, Parietal lobe, Temporal lobe, and Occipital lobe.

The Visual Cortex seats in the Occipital lobe which helps to see and process stimuli received from the external world. It also remembers and gives meaning to visual perceptions. Around 80% of the information from our surroundings that reaches to our brains comes from our Eyes.

The visual cortex works as the primary section that receives, incorporates, and processes visual information received by retina of the eye transmits.

Research has shown that there is an extensive connection between the amygdala and visual cortex as an amygdala plays a significant role in converting emotions, memories, and experiences by receiving information from the senses.

The amygdala processes all the acquired information and tells the body to react with particular response.

For example, if we see a lion in front of the eyes, it is quite common for us to feel fear and frightened. Similarly, if we are given a surprise gift, we become happy and show love and affection for the gift and person. If we could not see with our precious eyes, it would be much more difficult for our brains to automatically process information and react with an appropriate emotion.

Science and research have shown that when a person stays in stressful situation or in anger then amygdala gets trigger and eventually it affects our mind and vision as well. So, it is necessary to keep calm and relax our mind for the better eyesight.

3. Agni Tattva

In simple words, the Pancha Mahabhutas considers as five sense organs through which we perceive the external world. They are the Eyes, Ears, Nose, Skin and Tongue.

According to Ayurveda, Agni also means 'Tejas' which means light. Agni tattva is responsible for the perception of Roopa, which is associated with sense organs.

Agni tattva is responsible for the digestion, heat, and metabolism in the body. Agni is also responsible in development of vision ability in the foetus while growing up. If heat increases in the body, it can affect the vision ability of person. So, during the research study, all the subjects were advised to avoid spicy, acidic and junk food consumption which can increase the heat (Agni) in the body. All the subjects were given protocol to balance the heat and consumption of such foods which can improve eye vision.

4. Trigunas & Tridoshas

The world is also considering creation of the three gunas – Sattva, Rajas and Tamas. Our vision for the external world is influenced by the three gunas. Examine your eye. The outer rim of the eye is red – which represents ‘Rajas Guna,’ then the white area – represents ‘Sattva Guna,’ the black circle in the centre – represents ‘Tamas Guna.’ That is why our vision is impaired by the three colours red, white, and black.

Alochaka Pitta from Types of Pitta Dosha

It is the subtype of pitta which is responsible for sight and understating process is known as alochaka pitta. Alochaka pitta resides in the retina of the eyes, which governs optical perception required for vision. It is responsible for dilation and contraction of pupil giving clarity and clear perception. It gives lustre to the eyes.

Pitta increases during the long and hot days of summer which causes eye strain and fatigue. When pitta is imbalance in the eyes, it affects the ability of our vision. So, it is necessary to take extra care of eyes during summer season.

The factors which can aggravate alochaka pitta are salty, sour, and spicy food, exposure of excess heat and dehydration. Loss of water in the body can increase fire element and pitta in the body.

So, all the subjects were given home remedies to reduce the heat in the body and gives cooling effects to the eyes.

The simple remedy shared with the subjects as daily schedule was to apply shredded Cucumber/ Bottle Gourd/ Potato on the eyes for 15 - 20 mins once a day. Along with this remedy, washing

eyes and face with cold water, with mouth full of water few times a day also helped to reduce tiredness of eyes. The cool temperature reduces blood flow while hydrating the delicate skin around the eyes, making eyes muscles relax.

5. Satvik Food and Sleep

Eye-friendly diet suggestions were given to all subjects. Research has proved that the diet including high fat and cholesterol enriched food can contribute to development of eye diseases which leads to loss of vision. Our eye vision also gets affected by gut health.

Food plays a vital role as natural energy source for the body. Diet has a considerable influence on our vision. A well-balanced diet helps to maintain healthy weight and avoid health conditions like obesity and diabetes which may affect the vision and lead to vision loss. A diet rich in vitamins and minerals protects vision. A diet high in fruits and vegetables but also low in saturated fats and sugar is a boon for the eyes.

Vitamins for Eye health

- **Beta- Carotene & Vitamin A**

These two substances work together to maintain eye health. Beta- carotene in the body converts into vitamin A, which helps keep the cornea clear. The cornea covers the eyes.so, these are important vitamins for eye health and vision. Vitamin A helps in the prevention of night blindness by allowing better eye adjustment in dark conditions. Consumption of Apple, Carrots, Beetroot, Berries, Papaya helps to prevent cataracts and macular degeneration and improve eye vision.

- **Lutein & Zeaxanthin**

Lutein and zeaxanthin are essential for vision and health of the retina. The only carotenoids located in the eye. All green leafy vegetables, orange pepper, kiwi, grapes contain substantial amounts of lutein and zeaxanthin. Studies have shown that lutein and zeaxanthin reduce the risk of chronic eye diseases like age-related macular degeneration and cataracts, also protect the eyes from sun damage.

- **Vitamin C**

Vitamin C promotes collagen, a protein that builds the structure of the eyes. Research has shown that when Vitamin C is taken in combination with other essential nutrients, it can slow the progression of age- related macular degeneration and visual acuity loss. Oranges, kiwi, strawberries, grapefruit, papaya, lemon, amla tomatoes, green peppers and many more citrus fruits and veggies are excellent source of Vitamin C.

- **Vitamin E**

Along with gorgeous skin, vitamin E is powerful antioxidant and an essential supplement for eye health. It helps to protect vision by guarding eyes against damage caused by free radicals. It is found in small quantities in food and is challenging to get enough vitamin E from food. Food sources are vegetable oils, almonds, pecan peanuts, wheat germ and sunflower seeds.

- **Vitamin D**

Vitamin D is essential for immunity and overall health support, including in the eyes. That is why ‘Sungazing’ is one of the best exercises for eyes while sun is rising or setting, and it is in orange – red colour.

➤ **Zinc**

Zinc considers as an essential trace mineral or helper molecule. It plays a key role in bringing vitamin A from the liver to the retina in order to produce melanin – a protective pigment in the eyes. Zinc found in food sources like fortified breakfast cereals and all types of Berries.

➤ **Omega-3 Fatty Acids**

Omega-3 fatty acids help build cell membranes in the retina. They contain anti-inflammatory properties that help protect the body from damage. Best sources are fatty- plant based food, tofu, brussels sprouts.

Circadian Rhythm from SLEEP portion

Human circadian rhythms are natural biological processes which regulates 24-hour cycles in the body. Circadian rhythms help determine our sleep patterns. It is controlled by the hypothalamus, which will send out signals and chemicals entire day to coordinate various functions in the body based on biological clock. The exposure of light to retina gives signals of alertness to brain which help to keep the body awake and active during daytime. With the setting of sun, light starts fading and the body will initiate the process of sleep. It is the sensory information given by eyes and connection to the hypothalamus.

According to sun rise and sun set, the light- dark cycle also starts in the retina. On receiving the signals, hypothalamus starts releasing melatonin from the pineal gland at night. The pineal gland is neuroendocrine gland that synthesizes and secretes melatonin. Some melatonin is also produced within some ocular cells. Melatonin is essential in regulating sleep patterns. Melatonin also referred as the sleep hormone.

Research has shown melatonin itself is used as a therapy for certain sleep disorders. Apart from sleep cycle, melatonin is involved in cell protection, neuroprotection and the reproductive system. Shift workers – who work during night-time, often struggle with sleep difficulties due to disturb circadian rhythm.

During my research study, all the subjects were advised to take proper eight hours sleep. Also, the benefits of sleeping in dark and secretion of melatonin were explained in detail to them for a sound sleep.

6. Enlightening Psycho Neurobics & RajaYoga

Enlightening neurobics is associated with Ajna /Agya Chakra also known as ‘Third Eye Chakra.’ The third eye is the greatest gift that connects us to the supreme soul and gives the experience of the mystical world beyond our physical senses. It can be attained through the awakening of the third eye and its corresponding pineal gland as sixth sense.

The Spiritual Significance of the Third Eye

The third eye also known as an inner eye is a mystical and occult concept. It opens the gateway of inner dimensions and spaces of higher consciousness. The third eye in reality is the pineal gland. Pineal gland is a pea-sized gland shaped like a pinecone, resides in the middle of the

brain. The third eye chakra is located in the centre of the forehead, between two eyes, near the pineal gland. Awakenning the third eye is the gateway to all psychic abilities – telepathy, clairvoyance, lucid dreaming, and astral projection. Without a mastery of this chakra, spiritual connections are not possible. The third eye is part of subtle body. Through this eye awakening we can experience to enter in different dimension and see things which are invisible to the physical eyes.

The Third Eye symbolizes enlightenment. In the Upanishads, a human being is likened to a city with ten gates. Nine gates are eyes, ears, nostrils, mouth, urethra, and anus lead to the sensory world. The third eye is the tenth gate which leads to inner vision and connection to the divine.

The Enlightening Neurobics is done with visualizing Indigo Color and holding Pran Mudra with both hands. This mudra is referred as the life force seal. Pran mudra is specifically used to activate dormant energy within the subtle body, balancing elements earth, water, and fire in the physical body. It also helps to clear energetic blockages, increasing vitality. This mudra decreases pitta dosha by reducing heat in the body. As prana vayu resides in the head and chest areas and is responsible for sensory perception and inhalation, it helps to improve circulation around the eye muscles and by strengthening the optic nerves also improves vision and eye health.

Blissful Neurobics

Blissful Neurobics is associated with Crown Chakra. It is done by visualizing Violet color and with humming sound, applying tongue to the palate. It is also known as ‘Khechari Mudra.’

The seven chakras of the human body form a junction at the throat. This intersection acts as a valve and prevents the flow of ‘Prana’ into the higher chakras. When we press the tongue against the throat, it locks this valve so that the prana can flow into the higher chakras – the Third Eye Chakra and the Crown Chakra easily without any obstacle. This free flow of prana awakens the mind to different spiritual experiences.

Khechhari Mudra also refers as king of all mudras, as it activates the Third eye. It helps to reach higher levels of consciousness.

As upper chakras also open and activates with positivity and gratitude, following Positive Affirmations and prayer of Gratitude with visualization were also practiced by all the subjects during the exercise of Neurobics to improve eye health.

- My Eyes and My Vision are Getting Better & Better Every day in Every Way. (Repeat 3 Times)
- I have Perfect, Crystal-Clear Vision
- I have Perfect, Bright, Shiny Eyes.

➤ **Forgiveness Prayer and Gratitude for Eyes**

'I Love you, My Eyes.

I am Sorry.

Please Forgive Me.

Thank you for Forgiving Me.

I Respect You.

I love you, My Eyes.'

(Visualize and feel that we have perfect Eyes and Vision during entire process).

Neurobic Spa

Neurobic Spa is the truthful way of connecting yourself with the Supreme Soul (God). With this unique meditation our seven energy centres get cleaned and filled with divine energy giving immense relaxation to the mind and body. Neurobic Spa was given in daily schedule to all the subjects before sleeping at night to clear the mind from day-to-day stress and for the maximum benefit of relaxation of mind and body.

For the process of Neurobic Spa, please refer (**Neurobic Spa' from Chapter No. 6 – Psycho Neurobics & Rajayoga.**)

7. Pranayama and Eye Exercises

Pranayama is one of the simple and best breathing exercise to direct, control prana energy/ breath in the body. Breathing is an involuntary act, which we can not control entire time, but we can control to some extent, the way we breath.

While doing Eye Exercises along with breathing, it gives direction to energy and gives maximum relaxation to the muscles around the eyes and optic nerves for better blood flow and to improve eye health.

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